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List of ICME-related Forbush decreases

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List of Acronyms

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
CDAWeb	Coordinated Data Analysis Web
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
COSPIN	Cosmic Ray and Solar Particle Instrument
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument (on-board SOHO)
E6	Experiment 6
FD	Forbush Decrease
FDAT	Forbush decrease analysis tool
FR	Flux rope
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HET	High Energy Telescope
ICME	Interplanetary coronal mass ejection
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
MAVEN	Mars Atmosphere and Volatile Evolution
MSL	Mars Science Laboratory
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NEST	NMDB event search tool
NM	neutron monitor
NMDB	Neutron Monitor Database
RAD	Radiation Assessment Detector
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SoIO	Solar Orbiter
SoPo	South Pole neutron monitor station
SPDF	Space Physics Data Facility
WP	Work Package
SOAR	Solar Orbiter Archive
EPD	Energetic Particle Detector
CAU	Christian-Albrechts-Universität
FD	Forbush Decrease

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents compilation of the catalogs of FDs related to the flux rope parts of Interplanetary coronal mass ejection (ICME)s detected throughout the Heliosphere by SOHO / EPHIN, neutron monitors, Helios/ Experiment 6 (E6), SoHO / High Energy Telescope (HET), MSL / RAD, and Ulysses / Kiel Electron Telescope (KET). A graphical user interface Forbush decrease analysis tool (FDAT) was used to compile the catalogs by systematically changing the time-interval and spacecraft. To confirm that the identified FDs are ICME flux rope-related, where possible, in situ plasma and magnetic field data was analysed. Thus, ICME properties such as average magnetic field, speed of propagation, speed of expansion, and radial expansion factor were derived. We used existing lists and catalogs of ICME and FD events for crosscheck. Each measurement has a unique identifier, which holds information on the date of the event, spacecraft and the observer. The FDAT output consists of plots and measurement files for each entry, as well as a .csv file with compiled measurements for all events. Full set of measurements is available in a google drive directory¹. The catalogs (together with a readme file) are available in the SPEARHEAD's internal repository nextcloud. The catalogs contain cca 1000 events throughout Heliosphere.

¹https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1khu9ccJRpZZh4iw_KjpJy8QGIZGyoemn?usp=share_link

1 Introduction

One of the common signatures of ICMEs in the heliosphere are FDs, short-term depressions in the Galactic Cosmic Ray (GCR) flux. FDs caused by ICMEs often show a two-step profile, one associated with the turbulent and compressed shock/sheath region ahead of the ICME magnetic structure and the other with the ICME magnetic structure itself (Cane 2000). Because of their different physical properties, the mechanism through which these two regions produce the depression is different (Papaioannou et al. 2020) and thus should be modelled differently. The current paradigm is that the CME magnetic structure is flux rope, a structure with field lines helicoidally winding around a central axis (e.g. Lundquist 1951). It was first proposed by Morrison (1956) that FDs might be caused by clouds of closed magnetised plasma, where they are initially empty of particles and slowly fill as they propagate through the interplanetary space. This approach has been since utilised to explain FR-associated FDs, where the particles are allowed to enter via "cross-field" transport, i.e. perpendicular diffusion (e.g. Cane et al. 1995; Quenby et al. 2008). In addition to the particle diffusion, another important contribution comes from the expansion of the Flux rope (FR). Namely, as they propagate through the IP space, CMEs expand due to the pressure imbalance (e.g. Klein & Burlaga 1982; Démoulin & Dasso 2009), where, consequently, as the size of the magnetic structure increases, its magnetic field weakens (e.g. Bothmer & Schwenn 1998; Démoulin et al. 2008). It was first proposed by Laster et al. (1962) and Singer et al. (1962) that expansion is needed to explain the observational properties of FDs. More recently the diffusion-expansion approach was applied by Munakata et al. (2006) and Kuwabara et al. (2009) in a numerical model and by Subramanian et al. (2009) and Arunbabu et al. (2013) in an analytical model, considering isotropic self-similar expansion. In the recent Forbush decrease analytical model ForbMod (Dumbović et al. 2018) different types of expansion are considered for the expansion-diffusion approach, constrained by observational ranges of the expansion factors (Gulisano et al. 2012).

Figure 1: A sketch of the CME flux rope in the interplanetary space with associated shock and sheath (left) and the corresponding synthetic measurements expected to be observed in situ (right). The FD profile within the flux rope region in the bottom panel of the right plot is modelled by ForbMod. Taken from (Dumbović et al. 2020).

ForbMod is an analytical diffusion-expansion model, which assumes that the ICME magnetic structure (i.e. flux rope) can locally be represented by a straight cylinder, initially empty of GCRs at its center. The

flux rope is assumed to be propagating at a constant speed, expanding self-similarly and the cosmic rays (protons) can only enter it via perpendicular diffusion. The ForbMod solution is a combination of the radial-dependent solution, which is given by the cylindrical Bessel function of the zeroth-order, and the time-dependent solution, which is given by the exponential function. The amplitude of the FD, defined normalised to border conditions, depends on the diffusion rate of particles into the FR. The diffusion rate is governed by the behaviour of the magnetic field, which is generally decreasing due to expansion. Thus, the FD amplitude is expected to decrease with diffusion time (i.e. heliospheric distance), but the FD profile is always given by the cylindrical Bessel function of the zeroth-order and is symmetric. The diffusion rate of particles also depends on the particle energy, as higher-energy particles enter the flux rope more easily. Therefore, it is expected that the FD amplitude is energy-dependent and should appear differently in detectors with different energy-response (for details see [Dumbović et al. 2018, 2020](#)). The energy response of a certain detector can be obtained using the GEometry ANd Tracking (GEANT)-4 Monte Carlo simulation by assuming certain geometry and shielding (see e.g. [Köberle et al. 2024](#)). ForbMod was found to fit well FDs associated with the CME magnetic structure in several case-studies ([Dumbović et al. 2018](#); [Rodari et al. 2018](#); [Dumbović et al. 2019, 2020](#)), but we also found events where its applicability is questionable ([Freiherr von Forstner et al. 2021](#)). The ForbMod best-fit procedure was developed, where it was found that ForbMod can reliably fit FDs associated with the CME magnetic structure ([Dumbović et al. 2024](#)).

In the scope of SPEARHEAD we aim to catalog FDs related to the flux rope part of the ICME (WP5), to perform statistical analysis and to demonstrate its utility by applying it to ForbMod model (WP7). Here, we describe how the catalog was compiled using the newly developed FDAT tool. The document is organised as follows: in Section 2 we describe the FDAT tool, in Section 3 we describe the data used and in Section 4 we describe compilation and content of the catalogs.

2 Forbush Decrease Analysis Tool (FDAT)

The Forbush Decrease Analysis Tool (FDAT) is a comprehensive Python PyQt5-based interface designed for the analysis of ICMEs and their associated FDs. The tool processes multi-instrument in-situ spacecraft observations to characterize magnetic field, plasma and GCR data.

FDAT currently supports 4 primary analysis modes:

- **ForbMod Analysis:** Fitting of Forbush decrease profiles using ForbMod best-fit procedure + General measurements of ICME and FD parameters;
- **In-situ Analysis:** General measurements of ICME parameters;
- **Sheath Analysis:** Detailed examination of ICME upstream/sheath/frontal/MO regions with optional Lundquist flux rope fitting;
- **Lundquist fitting:** Application of the Lundquist fit for the flux rope.

The tool currently supports data from multiple spacecraft as well as ground-based measurements (for details see Section 3). The tool follows a modular, data-driven architecture with clear separation between:

- **User Interface Layer:** PyQt5 windows and dialogs
- **Data Management Layer:** CDF file handling and caching
- **Analysis Layer:** Scientific calculations and fitting routines
- **Output Layer:** File generation and result persistence

The tool architecture is given by the diagram below:

The user enters the application by running `FDAT_main.py` which opens the Graphical User Interface (GUI) Start window. The Application Entry is configured by Settings Manager. In the Start Window the user chooses the spacecraft and timeframe, as well as analysis type. A screenshot of the Start Window is given in Figure 2.

Forbush Decrease Analysis Tool

Analyze ICME and Forbush Decrease events

Observer: Analysis type: ForbMod In-situ Sheath Lundquist fit

Start Date (yyyy/mm/dd):

End Date (yyyy/mm/dd):

Select Satellite:

WIND Nov 1994 - Sep 2024	ACE Sep 1997 - Dec 2022	SatD Apr 2020 - Jul 2024
OMNI Jan 1998 - Dec 2024	neutron monitors Jan 1998 - Dec 2024	MAVEN Dec 2014 - Dec 2023
Ulysses Nov 1990 - Jul 2009	Helios-1 Dec 1974 - Jun 1981	Helios-2 Jun 1976 - Mar 1980

Start Analysis

Figure 2: A screenshot of the Start Window in FDAT.

Figure 3: A screenshot of the Visualisation Window for ForbMod analysis mode in FDAT.

Once chosen, GUI loads the data and the Data Visualisation window opens, in which the user defines regions to perform the analysis. Once this is chosen, the tool automatically performs pre-set calculations and saves the results in the output file. The pre-set calculations may be modified by changing the JSON-based configuration files (for advanced users only). Output is saved in standardized CSV format with publication-quality figures. FDAT is available through SPEARHEAD Github: <https://github.com/spearhead-he/FDAT>. Details on download/installation, running, updating and general technical details are given on the FDAT Github.

In SPEARHEAD only ForbMod analysis mode is used. In this mode, the user marks start and end of the region where they want to measure ICME/FD properties and apply ForbMod best fit. Once the region is chosen the measurement and calculation is performed automatically. This allows fast screening of data to identify and measure ICMEs/FDs as well as perform ForbMod best-fit (note that the latter is part of WP7, which is yet to start). A screenshot of the Visualisation Window for ForbMod analysis mode is given in Figure 3. Details of measured quantities are given in Section 4.

3 Data and Instrumentation

To compile a list of ICME-related FDs we use the following data/instruments:

- SOHO/EPHIN (Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) detector F, supplemented by the in-situ measurements of the magnetic field from Wind (MFI, Lepping et al. 1995) and Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE) (MAG, Smith et al. 1998), as well as corresponding plasma measurements from Wind (SWE, Ogilvie et al. 1995), i.e. from ACE (SWEPAM, McComas et al. 1998). SOHO/EPHIN data are provided by Christian-Albrechts-Universität (CAU), whereas magnetic field and plasma data are loaded from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) /Space Physics Data Facility (SPDF) /Coordinated Data Analysis Web (CDAWeb) database: <https://cdaweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>.
- NM / SoPo data supplemented by in-situ data from Wind and ACE, similarly as for SOHO/EPHIN data. SoPo data are taken from the Neutron Monitor Database (NMDB) NMDB event search tool (NEST): <https://www.nmdb.eu/nest/>.
- SolO/Energetic Particle Detector (EPD) instrument HET (Rodriguez-Pacheco et al. 2021) data from the single detector C, supplemented by the in-situ measurements of the magnetic field (MAG, Horbury et al. 2020) and plasma measurements (SWA, Owen et al. 2020). EPD data is provided by CAU, but also available through Solar Orbiter Archive (SOAR), whereas magnetic field and plasma data are loaded from the NASA /SPDF /CDAWeb database.
- Helios E6 (Kunow et al. 1974) data from detector D5, supplemented by in-situ measurements of the magnetic field (E2, Rosenbauer et al. 1977) and solar wind (E1, Neubauer et al. 1977). Helios/E6 data are provided by CAU, whereas Helios in situ plasma and magnetic field data are available as high-level data product from NASA /SPDF / COHOWeb database: <https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/coho/>.
- Ulysses Cosmic Ray and Solar Particle Instrument (COSPIN) (Simpson et al. 1992) KET data from channel P190, supplemented by the in-situ measurements of the magnetic field (VHM/FGM, Balogh et al. 1992) and plasma measurements (SWOOPS, Bame et al. 1992). KET data is provided by CAU, whereas Ulysses in situ plasma and magnetic field data are available as high-level data product from NASA /SPDF / COHOWeb database.
- RAD detector (Hassler et al. 2012), on board MSL's rover Curiosity (Grotzinger et al. 2012), supplemented by the in situ measurements of the magnetic field and plasma from MAVEN, processed using an algorithm described by Halekas et al. (2017) to avoid contamination from measurements taken inside the Mars bow shock.

More details on the particle detectors used here and data products is provided in Koeberle et al. (2025). All data is provided in the FDAT tool as CDF files and may be used independently of the tool. Particle data is given on an hourly resolution, whereas magnetic field/plasma data is given on a minute resolution (where possible) to facilitate ICME identification (primarily the observation of the smooth rotation). We note that the analysis of some of this data/instruments (e.g. Helios), as well as the FDAT tool used to perform analysis and measurements, was not foreseen in the course of SPEARHEAD, but we include it also in the SPEARHEAD repository/analysis for completeness, visibility and availability.

4 Compilation of Catalogs

All FD catalogues are currently only available within the project and can be assessed via the internal repository of SPEARHEAD at:

1. **SOHO/EPHIN:** <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/iM4KYfN7qLWB85S>
2. **Solo/HET:** <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/kn8R4b3ZBgCqkao>
3. **Helios 1/E6:** <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/WbpRcngKaDyp5xd>
4. **Helios 2/E6:** <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/q7aw42gCxNNdwj2>
5. **Ulysses/KET:** <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/AxNjTNpSKxaZX7p>
6. **MSL/RAD:** <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/WZ6RKGpJpcYmdQ6>
7. **NM/SoPo:** <https://files.spearhead-he.eu/index.php/s/mjqD42z2gMbmZfQ>

All catalogues will be made available at a later stage through a public repository, such as the SPEARHEAD Zenodo Community. This timeline allows the SPEARHEAD consortium sufficient opportunity to further investigate the scientific insights that the catalogues will enable during the course of the project.

4.1 Measurements

By systematically changing the time-interval and instrument, the entire lifespan of instruments/data described in Section 3 was visually inspected for ICME-related FDs and ForbMod best-fit procedure was applied.

For our analysis, we investigate the following in-situ parameters to identify ICMEs: the magnetic field strength, B , and its fluctuations, dB_{rms} ; the magnetic field components, B_x , B_y , and B_z (preferably, in RTN coordinate system); the plasma density, n , temperature, T , and expected temperature, T_{exp} ; the plasma flow speed, v , and plasma beta parameter, β .

ICMEs typically consist of the magnetic structure, which is presumably a flux rope (also referred to as magnetic ejecta, magnetic obstacle and in specific cases magnetic cloud) and a sheath region. The sheath region is a compressed and turbulent region in front of the flux rope, which typically causes the first depression in the FD. In this study, we are only interested in the flux rope part of the FD, i.e. the second depression. We identify the flux rope part of FD when some or all of the following properties are present (following typical properties as highlighted by e.g. Zurbuchen & Richardson 2006; Kilpua et al. 2017, and references therein): 1) smoothly rotating magnetic field (enhanced B , low dB_{rms} , one of the magnetic components changes sign from start to end); 2) low plasma temperature; 3) low plasma beta parameter; 4) monotonically decreasing plasma flow speed. To analyze FD, we use the associated GCR particle detector data, normalized to the pre-decrease value for each event.

To minimize observer bias, we perform measurements using three different interpretations of the ICME/FD event boundaries for each event, similar to that provided by Dumbović et al. (2024). The onset of FD is usually defined as the point where the GCR count starts to drop, while the end of FD, in a textbook example, would be the point where it returns to its pre-decrease level (e.g. Dumbović et al. 2011). In textbook examples, the recovery of two-step FD is prolonged after the passage of the ICME due to the a shading effect of the shock-sheath region, whereas for a FR, FD (which can be self-standing or a second decrease in a two-step FD), the end of FD corresponds to the end of the FR (Dumbović et al. 2020). However, in many non-textbook cases, the determination of the onset and end of FD is not a trivial procedure that can be defined by a simple algorithm applicable evenly to all events (Papaioannou et al. 2010; Belov et al. 2015). Therefore, the extraction of FD profiles (from the onset to the end) is

Figure 4: Example ICME event of 10 September 1997 detected by Wind and corresponding normalized GCR data from SOHO/EPHIN F-detector. Blue and red shaded areas indicate extended and inner ICME borders, respectively. In this example the inner ICME borders correspond to the optimal fit borders.

best performed manually by an observer. This may result in a certain subjectivity when determining the borders, especially the end of **FD**. Therefore, we apply three different versions of border selection:

- **extended ICME borders** - these encompass typical **ICME** signatures such as, for example, low temperature or low plasma beta, but with borders set based on the **GCR** depression onset or end and/or based on the total magnetic field increase onset or end. They thus overlap with typical **FR** signatures only in a subset of events, and they often contain external disturbed parts of the **FR** and/or show substructuring.
- **inner ICME borders** - we find that many events show clearer **FR** signatures in a subinterval of what would normally be selected as the global **FR** structure according to, for example, the low-beta condition. For some events it is possible to set **FD** borders corresponding to this inner part and these **FDs** are typically short-duration, shallower but of more symmetric shape.
- **optimal fit borders** - these are most subjectively chosen, as the observer puts the borders in a way that the best-fit curve visually nicely follows the data. This border selection serves as a control mechanism, but it will also be interesting how these borders compare to the other two selections.

Note that it is not always possible to make these three distinct border selections, as shown by [Dumbović et al. \(2024\)](#) and that optimal fit borders may in fact correspond to either extended ICME borders or optimal fit borders.

Figure 5: Six types of ForbMod fits to EPHIN data based on visual analysis: a) a good fit (event1, inner structure borders); b) an asymmetric fit (event1, extended ICME borders); c) a few-data-points fit (event2, inner structure borders); d) a large-scatter fit (event2, extended ICME borders); e) an under-recovery fit (event4, extended ICME borders); and f) a substructuring fit (event17, extended ICME borders). FD_{obs} was FD amplitude-determined using a traditional algorithm-based observational method, whereby FD was measured from the onset to the minimum. FD_{bf} is the FD amplitude obtained from the ForbMod best-fit procedure and MSE is the mean standard error. Figure taken from ([Dumbović et al. 2024](#)).

Once the borders are selected **FDAT** automatically calculates pre-set parameters (for full list see [Section 4.2](#)) and performs ForbMod best-fit to selected data. This opens the ForbMod best-fit window

where the fit is visualized and goodness-of-fit (i.e. mean standard error) is displayed. The observer then visually inspects the fit and assigns one or more of the following properties (based on procedure by [Dumbović et al. 2024](#)):

- **a good fit** - where there was visually a good match between data points and the best-fit function
- **an asymmetric fit** - where the fitted function was shifted along the x-axis compared to the data points
- **a few-data-points fit** - where the fit was performed on only a small number of data points
- **a large-scatter fit** - where the fit was performed on data points with a large scatter
- **an under-recovery fit** - where the data points did not return to the pre-decrease level
- **a substructuring fit** - where a single fit was performed while the data points indicated possible substructuring

Note that **FDAT** in addition has "no FD?", "no ICME" and "FD increase" as categories to be assigned to the event, but these will not be included in the SPEARHEAD analysis. Examples of fit types are given in Figures 5a-f taken from ([Dumbović et al. 2024](#)). However, we note that some events may fall into more than one category; for example, an event might show under-recovery as well as substructuring. Figure 6 illustrates the best-fit ForbMod curves for two types of fit borders in the example shown in Figure 4. The extended ICME borders fit is characterized as asymmetric and substructuring fit, whereas the inner ICME borders fit is characterized as substructured. Note that in this example both extended and inner ICME borders contain substructured **FD**.

Figure 6: ForbMod best-fit procedure result (red curve) for the ICME/FD event of 10 September 1997. Left: extended ICME borders. Right: inner ICME borders.

We used existing lists and catalogs of **ICME** and **FD** events for crosscheck with events we identified. This information is saved for each event. We note that we do not cross-check our events with *ALL* existing lists and catalogs, we only selected couple (2-3) of lists, preferably from independent groups. We also note that, due to specific properties of the events in our catalogs (**FD** related to only flux rope part of the ICME) there is no 1-1 relation with other catalogs. The catalogs which we cross-check are the following:

- [Belov et al. \(2021\)](#), [Richardson & Cane \(2010\)](#), [Nieves-Chinchilla et al. \(2018\)](#) for **SOHO/EPHIN** measurements
- [Blanco et al. \(2013\)](#), [Bothmer & Schwenn \(1998\)](#), and [Cane et al. \(1997\)](#) for Helios measurements
- Helio4cast² for **Solo** measurements

²<https://helioforecast.space>

- IZMIRAN FD list³ (Belov et al. 2015), Richardson & Cane (2010), Nieves-Chinchilla et al. (2018) for NM/SoPo measurements
- Guo et al. (2018) and Zhao et al. (2021) for MSL-RAD
- Richardson (2014) for Ulysses

Each measurement has a unique identifier, which holds information on the date of the event, spacecraft and the observer. The FDAT output consists of plots and measurement files for each entry, as well as a .csv file with compiled measurements for all events. Full sets of measurements are available in a google drive directory⁴. These are not public files. From these files catalogs are compiled which are stored in SPEARHEAD next cloud: ... which constitute SPEARHEAD public deliverable.

4.2 Description of the Catalogs entries

We compiled 7 separate catalogs for each of the instrument used to detect and best-fit FDs. The catalogs are saved in 7 .csv files named after the corresponding instrument: SOHO_EPHIN.csv, SoIO_HET.csv, HeliosI_E6.csv, HeliosII_E6.csv, Ulysses_KET.csv, MSL_RAD.csv, and NM_SoPo.csv. Each line, i.e. entry, in the catalog represents a single unique measurement/fit that was performed. Thus, for a single event there may be multiple entries. All catalogs are formatted identically, with a single readme file describing the columns. The description of the columns is as follows:

- **id**: unique identifier for each entry in all the catalogs consisting of connected strings holding information on observer, instrument, timing and border type:
FD_{SATELLITE}_{GCR_DETECTOR}_{OBSERVER_NAME}_{DATE}_{BORDER_TYPE}
- **year**: year of the start of the event
- **date**: date of the start of the event in the form yyyy_mm_dd
- **sat**: satellite performing in situ measurements
- **detector**: detector performing GCR measurements
- **dist [AU]**: heliocentric distance at which the measurements were performed in au
- **clong**: carrington longitude at which the measurements were performed in degrees
- **clat**: carrington latitude at which the measurements were performed in degrees
- **borders**: type of the border selection as described in Section 4.1 (extended, inner, optimal), where it is also possible to have 'test' for events that the observer wants to highlight or not include in the analysis
- **DOY Start**: the start time of the event, i.e. day-of-year (DOY) corresponding to the starting border of the measurement/fit
- **DOY End**: the end time of the event, i.e. day-of-year (DOY) corresponding to the ending border of the measurement/fit **DOY Fdmin**: day-of-year (DOY) corresponding to the minimum of FD with respect to the onset (starting border)
- **vAvg [km/s]**: average plasma flow speed in the interval between selected borders

³<http://spaceweather.izmiran.ru/eng/dbs.html>

⁴https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1khu9ccJRpZZh4iw_KjpJy8QGIZGyoemn?usp=share_link

- **vMedian**: median plasma flow speed in the interval between selected borders
- **vStdev** standard deviation of plasma flow speed in the interval between selected borders
- **vLead**: plasma flow speed at the leading edge, i.e. at the start time
- **v_center**: plasma flow speed in the center of the interval between selected borders
- **vTrail**: plasma flow speed at the trailing edge, i.e. at the end time
- **upstream_w**: 'quiet solar wind' plasma flow speed upstream of ICME arrival, calculated as average in the interval selected by the observer (not relevant for SPEARHEAD, but automatically calculated by [FDAT](#))
- **BPeak [nT]**: Maximum total magnetic field measured in the interval between selected borders
- **BAvg**: average total magnetic field in the interval between selected borders, in nT
- **BMedian**: median total magnetic field in the interval between selected borders, in nT
- **BStdev** standard deviation of total magnetic field in the interval between selected borders, in nT
- **FD_obs [%]**: [FD](#) amplitude measured from the onset to the minimum of [FD](#) (i.e. using standard [FD](#) amplitude determination)
- **FD_bestfit**: [FD](#) amplitude determined based on ForbMod best-fit
- **MSE**: mean square error of the fit, i.e. goodness-of-fit
- **fit type**: observers characterisation of the fit based on visual inspection, as described in Section [4.1](#) (good, asymmetric, few-data-points, large scatter, under-recovery, substructuring)
- **notes**: any notes given by the observer (typically contains information whether event is present in some of the catalogs and where)

4.3 Some remarks on the events in the catalogs

Some typical examples of measured [FDs](#) are given in [Figure 7](#). It can be seen that structured flux ropes with corresponding ForbMod-like depressions can be observed up to 1 AU. At Mars distances we rarely observe the flux rope part of the [FD](#) and the depression is dominantly caused by the shock/sheath of the [ICME](#). Finally, at Ulysses detection and fitting of the flux rope part of the [FDs](#) is hampered by very weak signatures in quite large [KET](#) noise (i.e. small signal-to-noise ratio) making the fit highly dependent on the border selection (even more than in other instruments). This is also likely linked to the fact that at such large distances [ICMEs](#) already expanded a lot and also have quite weak signatures ([Wimmer-Schweingruber et al. 2006](#); [Maunder et al. 2022](#)). We do however note that statistical analysis is needed to reliably characterize [FD](#) properties at different distances and instruments which will be performed in the upcoming period. We also note that the observers reported several interesting remarks regarding the events:

- In CME-CME interaction events [FD](#) corresponding to the 1st CME can usually be fitted (though underrecovery is almost always present), however, most of the time the following CMEs do not have clear [FD](#) structure to which the fit can be applied
- occasionally a small magnetic flux rope (SMFR) can be found with a corresponding [FD](#), which has a suitable profile for ForbMod fitting, these were included in the list with a note, however, we cannot confirm they are of solar origin.

Figure 7: Examples of measured FDs at: top left: Helios 1 0.33 AU 19-6-1981, bottom left: SoLo 0.5 AU 8-3-2022, top middle: OMNI/NM-SoPo 1 AU 13-3-2022, bottom middle: Wind/SOHO-EPHIN 1 AU 13-3-2022, top right: MAVEN/MSL-RAD 1.39 AU 18-1-2015, bottom right: Ulysses 5.25 AU 29-11-1998. The shaded area marks the flux-rope related FD part fitted by ForbMod (except for MAVEN/MSL-RAD where no flux-rope part of FD was observed and shaded area corresponds to the sheath).

- different border selection is not possible in all events and for many events only an optimal fit is found (following best FD profile)

These aspects will be taken into account when performing statistical analysis. Finally, the catalogues also contain ICME and FD analysis of events identified as relevant by Work Package (WP)4 (e.g. multi-spacecraft event observed at Earth by NMs and by SOHO at 1 AU and by SolO at 0.5 AU in March 2022).

5 Conclusions and Outlook

In this document, multiple catalogues of FDs related to the flux rope part of ICMEs have been compiled and presented, demonstrating results from the first 18 months of the SPEARHEAD project. The first release of these event catalogues is based on the scanning of Helios / E6, SoIo / HET, SOHO / EPHIN, NM / SoPo, MSL / RAD and Ulysses KET measurements. Therefore, the first SPEARHEAD catalogues provide a broad overview of FDs related to the flux rope part of ICMEs, directly addressing the third **Science Question - SQ** put forth by the project, namely:

- **SQ3: What are the key processes of high-energy particle transport in the interplanetary medium, in the magnetosphere and in the atmosphere?**

These catalogs provide FD properties — including amplitude and visual match to ForbMod-fitted profiles — alongside ICME properties and the distances at which they were detected, for a sample of about 1,000 events — a large and statistically significant dataset. Thus, this sample can be used to directly test underlying assumptions of FD models, such as ForbMod and thus reveal key processes of high-energy particle transport in the interplanetary medium.

This first release of the catalogues constitutes **Deliverable D5.3** of the project. Further releases may happen to include more events or revised data on the present events, where needed.

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